

The Use of Nominative Sentences in Literature

Makhmudov Muzaffar Mamirovich

Senior Teacher at University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

Email: muzaffar.makhmudov@yahoo.com

Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of nominative sentences from a communicative and functional perspective, with a focus on their role within a text. The author considers nominative constructions not as isolated syntactic units, but as full-fledged utterances functioning within coherent discourse. Special attention is given to the interaction of nominative sentences with context, the types of speech situations in which they are used, and the ways in which their incomplete predicative structure is semantically compensated. The significance of nominative constructions as tools of text formation and meaning actualization in literary and journalistic discourse is emphasized.

Keywords: nominative sentence, text, context, utterance, communicative function, explicitness, syntax, textual semantics, syntactic structure, speech situation.

1 Introduction

The expediency of studying nominative sentences implies an investigation of the functioning and role of these units in the process of communication, particularly in human speech behavior (communication participants). From this perspective, the communicative approach becomes important, based on the categories of semantics, syntactics, and paradigmatics. According to this approach, every language unit is studied in terms of its interrelation with meaning, compatibility with other units, and participation in the communication act between the “speaker” and the “listener.” A nominative sentence is not regarded as a specific structural model of a predicative construction, but rather as an utterance that fulfills certain functions in a coherent text (both dialogic and monologic). Currently, the functioning of nominative sentences in text has not been widely represented. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the specific use of nominative sentences in literary texts, which are the primary domain of their functioning.

In the language system, a nominative sentence is a construction that represents an aspect of a general situation, expressed by an utterance containing the general sense of being, existence, or presence. The non-discrete element of the semantic structure (represented by the predicate of existence) in a nominative sentence appears in unity with its bearer: the semantic elements of existing substance and being find a syncretic expression in one-part nominative sentences. Though non-discrete, being in nominative sentences is explicit. Such sentences display a special type of relationship between the content of the utterance and reality, which receives specific (explicit) formal expression in the text [4, p. 35].

2 Methods

At the textual level, where the sentence-utterance functions as a real unit, the relationship between nominative and full sentences takes the form of autosemantic/semantic connections. A nominative sentence can express concrete meanings even outside the context, but it functions fully only within a coherent text. The formation of meaning in an utterance is influenced not only by its content determined by the positional model of the sentence but also by the communicative situation, context, shared knowledge of the interlocutors (presupposition), and other factors. The recipient is able to extract significantly more information from the utterance, as a component of the text, than from a full sentence used in isolation [2, p. 162].

The relationship between the text and the nominative sentence is, in our view, an interesting issue due to the limited study of this phenomenon. Syntactic relations between the nominative sentence and the text have long been overlooked, although scholars such as V.G. Gak, G.A. Zolotova, N.D. Arutyunova, A.S. Popov, M.V. Kurovskaya, E.Yu. Ivanova, and others have addressed this issue at various times.

The connection between the nominative sentence and the text is evidenced by the fact that a nominative sentence, without reliance on neighboring sentences, does not express the semantics of being. Sentences like *Snow. Silence. convey nothing definite. They merely indicate the existence of snow and silence.* However, in interaction with the context, a new, previously undetectable meaning emerges. Compare: *Snow and Snow. Finally, real winter has begun! or Snow. Look, it’s snowing! // Silence and Silence. The city seems asleep.*

B.M. Gasparov writes: “The theory of text as we know it today offers nothing for the typology of sentences... Likewise, it does not make use of existing classifications of sentences independent of text descriptions” [1, p. 46]. Referring to sentence structure, B.M. Gasparov denies the possibility of linking a sentence’s syntactic composition with its surroundings, basing his conclusions on the idea that “the structure of a sentence is not a constitutive feature of inter-sentence connection” [1, p. 49]. Considering the nominative sentences *Winter night. A road running along the forest. Silence,* B.M. Gasparov notes that “this sequence can easily be transformed by breaking the parallelism without disrupting its unity”: *Winter night. A hunter walks along the forest. Complete silence reigns.*

We agree with G.A. Zolotova, who disagrees with this view and emphasizes that lexical (more precisely, categorial-semantic) changes in this case are not insignificant, as they can alter the text itself [3, pp. 113–114].

Let us compare B.M. Gasparov’s transformation with the lexical substitutions proposed by G.A. Zolotova: *Winter night. A hunter walks along the forest. A full woman stands.* Although the external parallelism of constructions is preserved, the unity of the sequence is broken. Between the sentences *A hunter walks along the forest. A full woman stands,* there is a lack of a connecting link indicating the perception or localization of the second character by the first: A hunter walks along the forest and sees a full woman.

The structural type of the construction is also perceived differently: the descriptive “chain” shifts to a narrative, which dictates other ways of linking the elements of the whole. Thus, the connection between sentences within the context is essential. Communicative-semantic modifications of models represented by one-part sentences like *Winter night. A road running along the forest. Silence* is similar to the models *Winter night. A hunter walks along the forest. Complete silence reigns,* which also consist of one-part constructions that state the presence of objects or states in a descriptive speech type. Both constructions are brought together through the structural-semantic component analysis presented above. However, they are contrasted with two-part constructions that report on an object and its predicative feature, such as *Winter night. A hunter walks along the forest. A full woman stands.*

Thus, nominative sentences, although syntactic units in their own right, demonstrate their functionality only when integrated into context. The emergence of such constructions is conditioned by the text. Therefore, a nominative sentence must be defined in relation to the text.

A nominative sentence, functioning as a textual unit, is an utterance whose structure includes some verbalized component of existential semantics, resulting from adaptation to the context.

The role of the text in interpreting linguistic units is substantial, since speech predominantly contains utterances with high degrees of explicitness and verbalization. Nominative sentences cannot exist in isolation from their surroundings or outside of verbal communication, because it is the context—semantically expressed by the formal side of speech—that reveals their meaning and the situation as a whole. Depending on their functions, several types of verbal context are distinguished: everyday, metaphorical, and situational.

3 Conclusion

We consider the nominative sentence as a textual-level element. Its lack of elements essential for a full two-part sentence is due to the conditions of its textual functioning. A nominative sentence is an utterance that, in the course of its formation, acquires the necessary meaning and structural components within the framework of the text.

For nominative sentences involved in shaping the meaning of the text, the surrounding context includes not only the verbal text itself but also the extralinguistic conditions of verbal activity. Linguistic context and communicative-speech situations together form a unified text that emerges during communication. Text components are perceived in the general flow as elements of discourse. The completion of a sentence’s meaning may occur within a microtext or in a larger text (dialogic unity, complex syntactic whole) that describes a general situation.

Thus, a nominative sentence is part of the text, interacts with it, adds additional meaning to it, and is itself compensated for by the surrounding context. As part of the text—whether a complex syntactic whole, a dialogic unity, or a complex sentence—its semantics unfolds and its meaning- and text-forming role is realized.

Used Literature

1. Gasparov, B.M. Oral Speech as a Semiotic Object. In: Semantics of Nomination and Semiotics of Oral Speech. Russian Colloquial Syntax: Collection of Scientific Works. Moscow, 1976. pp. 46–48.
2. Zvegintsev, V.A. Language and Linguistic Theory. Moscow: Editorial URSS, 2001. 162 p.
3. Zolotova, G.A. Communicative Aspects of Russian Syntax. Moscow, 2001. pp. 113–114.
4. Mokrousova, O.Yu. The Nominative Sentence as a Text Unit: Communicative and Pragmatic Aspect: Monograph. Germany: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing GmbH & Co. KG, 2012. 192 p.
5. Bobojonova, S. (2024). Muloqot va uning pragmatik tahlili. Modern Science and Research, 3(1), 1-5.
6. Problems in the Study of One-Member Sentences: Collective Monograph. Moscow: "Prometheus", Moscow City Pedagogical University, 2005. 240 p.
7. Бобожонова, Ш. Ю. (2019). Роль нового поколения учебно-методической литературы в обеспечении качества знаний студентов по английскому языку. Наука и образование сегодня, (5 (40)), 67-68.
8. Khabitovich, O. B. (2024). RELEVANCE OF GENDER TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND LEARNING, 2(3), 247-257.
9. Omonov, B. (2020). INVESTIGATING THE THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF STUDYING TERMS IN LINGUISTICS. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
10. Kizi, S. B. Y. (2022). Linguo-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette occurring in discourse. Current Research Journal of Philological Sciences, 3(11), 59-63.
11. Makhmudov, M. . (2024). THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 4(12 Special Issue), 38–41. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/43511>